

The Impact of the Digital Economy on the Hotel Industry

Frangiza A. Abdullaeva

Chairman of the Association of Hoteliers of Uzbekistan, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: The article analyzes online tourism, its opportunities, the state of development in Uzbekistan. Based on the results of the study, proposals were developed to solve the problems that hinder the development of online tourism in the country. Including:

- commercial banks in the country should also ensure the security of money transfers, as well as improve the system of short-term refunds in case of cancellation, refund or replacement of numbers and tickets;
- all payment accounts must operate in a biometric system;
- more effective use of bloggers in promoting the tourism potential of the country.

KEYWORDS: online tourism, internet, payment security, travelers, air and train tickets, museums, hotels and hostels.

INTRODUCTION

It would not be a mistake to say that today there is no industry or network that does not include elements of e-commerce. In particular, in the modern era, buying a plane ticket, booking a hotel, renting a car, paying for a tour is done with a few clicks of the mouse. It is these factors that create the conditions for the development of online tourism.

Online tourism is a new form of promotion of tourism products, a direction in which representatives of the tourism industry, regardless of their location, offer a tourist product to a group of customers, mainly through the Internet. Online tourism helps a tourist, tour operator or travel agent make a decision using an electronic tool. Even in its formative and developmental stages, the tourism industry has benefited greatly from online tourism in certain countries. With the advent of the Internet, the online tourism industry has gained significant momentum. In a short period of time, the Internet has proved its worth in the use of tourism opportunities with the use of modern communication technologies. This has led to e-marketing, popularly known as e-marketing or internet marketing.

The development of online tourism not only reduces the time spent for travelers, but also saves money. For this reason, the number of enthusiasts in this segment is growing among travelers around the world.

According to experts, e-tourism provides the following opportunities:

1. Save time. The tourist does not have to go anywhere, get stuck in traffic and discuss the tour for a long time.
2. Innovation. Online travel services are among the first to offer new technologies related to hotel booking, paperwork and route connection. Sometimes they develop programs and tools themselves.
3. Online tours. Through online tours, you will have the opportunity to preview and get acquainted with the place you are visiting.

Online tourism has brought about a number of changes in the tourism industry, the main impact of which has been on the interdependence between service providers and traditional intermediaries. He invited tourists from all over the world to express their needs, search for directions, amenities, prices, geographical and weather information for various tourism products and services. In addition, it has the advantage in searching for information or details about tourists, market trends, service providers, routes, amenities, prices, tour packages, and maintaining direct contact with their partners. Undoubtedly, online tourism has emerged successfully as a platform that allows direct booking, electronic payments, Business to Business (B2B) and Business to Consumer (B2C) sales between product sellers, travel agencies and customers. The Internet and related developments have played an important role in the growth of online tourism and the online economy.

It should also be noted that e-tourism has further developed as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic. The number of virtual tours has increased. As a result of virtual tours, real estate is sold 9 percent more expensive and 30 percent faster [1].

The Impact of the Digital Economy on the Hotel Industry

Uzbekistan is also taking measures to develop online tourism during the Covid-19 pandemic. In particular, it is planned to launch online-tourism.uz. The launch of this site will allow you to make virtual trips around Uzbekistan.

There was also an opportunity to purchase and issue air and rail tickets online.

VRONICA is creating a virtual database of all museums in Uzbekistan. Google Arts & Culture is an online collection of exhibits from 1,200 museums, galleries and other organizations in 70 countries around the world. The Foundation for the Development of Culture and Arts was one of the first in Uzbekistan to partner with this platform.

The official websites of hotels operating in the country are functioning, and booking rooms through these sites is also developed. At <https://mybooking.uz/ru> you can get information about hotels and recreation areas in Tashkent, Samarkand, Khiva, Bukhara and other cities. Through the popular and widely used site <https://www.booking.com>, which is popular among international tourists, it is possible to book rooms and make payments in hotels of the country from different parts of the world.

But all this is not enough for the development of online tourism in the country. Including:

- There is no single e-database of hotels, hostels, guest houses, restaurants in the country (some restaurants do not even have corporate websites);
- The difficulty of returning or exchanging air and rail tickets through online databases;
- Insecurity of online payments, etc.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Online tourism is one of the most widely studied topics in the 21st century by experts in this field.

In particular, among the CIS scientists E. V. Vishnevskaya [3]. According to his scientific views, the main reason for the development of online tourism is the value of the services of tour operators, the desire of tourists to organize trips in the desired direction.

In the research of EF Gamilyanova, the Internet plays a key role in every stage of online tourism (not just online tourism). Social networks also play an important role in the organization of tourism and will be important in the organization of tourism marketing [4].

In Sofronov's research, online tourism benefits small and independent businesses, as well as well-known brands. mentioned [5].

The advent of online technology has begun to support tourism operations in many ways in many countries. Planning routes, pricing, tickets, accommodation, etc. While full convergence is expected in the future, these technologies are important in raising awareness and availability and reducing uncertainty about communication gaps. While there are high forecasts for all areas of tourism in the future, technology may not help us better manage our tourism operations. These ideas Manoj Dixit, Dr. Rakesh Belwal, Dr. This is reflected in Gurmeet Singh's research entitled "Online tourism and travel- analyzing trends from marketing perspective" [6].

RESULTS

In the era of modern development of the global tourism industry, online tourism is an important segment. This segment itself also includes several directions. For example, an online information system that includes hotels, rail and air tickets, tourist destinations, place names and maps, and more.

Despite obstacles and doubts, online tourism is designed to re-engineer most of the processes that support all travel and excursions. As a result of organizational information systems and the Internet, new ways and means of doing business have emerged, such as the development of e-commerce and e-market spaces.

Airlines, travel intermediaries, travel sites and the hotel industry are key players in online tourism. Analyzing each of these components, we observe the following:

Airlines

It has emerged as an integral part of the lives of international or domestic travelers. As a result, transportation capacity has become crucial in the development or expansion of any route. Airlines, which serve as a means of achieving frequent and high transport capacity, have played an important role in giving a major impetus to the tourism industry.

In general, the internet has been a great help to these airlines in reducing the length of their distribution channel. The cheap airlines that have emerged in the last few years are spending huge sums of money to distribute flight tickets directly to customers online. Even large global airlines are realizing that the online channel will provide a unique opportunity to reduce costs and restore profitability in this area, increasing financial efficiency.

The Impact of the Digital Economy on the Hotel Industry

Many of the world's leading airlines are now posting on the internet based on their efforts in the process of building and changing relationships with customers and other marketing intermediaries. These airlines are spending large sums of money to develop web operations in order to increase the share of tickets sold online, manage the supply chain and reduce purchase costs.

In our country, a system of booking and purchasing tickets through the site www.uzairways.com [7] has been established, but there are still problems with the return of air tickets.

Travel intermediaries

In the past, the interaction of tourists with tourism service providers has gradually turned the tourism industry into a tour operator center, where route planning has developed as an absolute necessity for them. This is leading to the emergence of a network of tour operators and travel agencies around the world, as well as one of the reasons for the organization of the industry online and directly using advanced technologies.

Travel agencies still play an important role in many parts of the world. Travel agencies around the world need to adapt to the new internet era, not just by acting as "travel information and product managers" instead of travel ticket sellers.

Online booking options are constantly beating offline options. A 2019 study found that 50 percent of shoppers said they were ready to use an online agency website and 59 percent said they were ready to use a hotel website. Thus, the shares of travel agents who want to continue in the traditional style remain under threat. However, better offers may emerge for those who want to use new technologies.

Hotel industry

Hotel and restaurant sites are also actively involved in online booking. They have been attracting many buyers in recent years as a result of offering new offers, room design, food preparation, prices and their diversification through their sites.

There are 833 hotels in Uzbekistan [8], each with its own website.

For example, in the case of the Hyatt Regency Tashkent, the website of the hotel includes rooms, their photos, vacant rooms and conditions for booking them, as well as additional options for consumers.

The official website of the Radisson Blu Hotel, Tashkent, describes the appearance, conditions, prices and booking options of standard, business class, semi-deluxe, deluxe, presidential suites [10].

However, this is not the case with the official websites of restaurants in Uzbekistan. Most of them don't have their own website, the ads are mostly done through social media and consumer quotes. There is also an opportunity to get information about 30 cafes and restaurants in Tashkent through the website <https://www.tripadvisor.ru/> [11].

There are also sites that are widely used around the world, used in the process of booking hotels, hostels and exchanges. Including:

Airbnb. It is a popular site that contains advertisements of individuals, which allows you to easily and quickly find the owners of apartments and houses. It serves as a very good resource for finding great apartments abroad.

Booking.com. The largest site in the world for finding and booking hotels and hostels. Many travelers choose this site because of its huge database of options, honest reviews, good prices, and excellent support. It is very convenient for those who plan to travel to Europe, North and Latin America, Australia. The best database for searching hotels for Asia is Agoda.com. Hostelworld.com also has an excellent hostel database.

Home exchange. The database contains more than 65,000 homes in 150 countries around the world. If you own your own home, you can exchange your home with property owners in another country during the holidays. The service has been available since 1992, and it all started with a book catalog of those who want to change homes.

Similar tourist sites are used in Uzbekistan. In particular, the website <https://uzbekistan.travel/ru/> operates in Uzbekistan. This site operates in 15 languages of the world, through which the country's attractions, "Uzbekistan. Safe travel GUARANTEED" system, along with the map of Uzbekistan, it is possible to make online trips to 29 tourist centers in Uzbekistan. It is also possible to get acquainted online with resorts, pilgrimage sites, archeological monuments, madrasas and museums.

DISCUSSION

Although measures are being taken to develop online tourism in the country, there are still challenges that hinder the development of this segment. Including:

- Risks in the process of registration of services. Confirmation of personal orders is done online, which means that any fraud and malfunctions in the system can be encountered.

- price volatility. Price changes can be prices several times a day;

- exchange / return of tickets. Tickets purchased online are non-refundable and non-exchangeable. Of course, this is not officially the case, but in fact exchanging or returning a ticket is one of the most difficult processes;

The Impact of the Digital Economy on the Hotel Industry

- The cost of Internet services in the country. In the country in 2020 it amounted to 45.0 thousand soums (\$ 4.3) per 1 Mbit / s. The number of Internet users in Uzbekistan has exceeded 22.1 million. Of these, the number of mobile Internet users is 19 million.

- Incomplete sites of restaurants and cafes in the country, inconsistencies between the services provided and the services offered online, the lack of online booking.

- online payment. Lack of security of plastic card or credit card information in the process of making online payments, multiple withdrawals of payments, etc.

Efforts of the Tourism Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan are not enough to promote the country's tourism potential and develop online tourism. and will need to be numbered.

In addition, commercial banks in the country will also need to improve the security of money transfers, as well as the system of short-term refunds in the event of cancellation, refund or replacement of rooms and tickets.

Although the country has a biometric passport system, not all payment accounts are attached to this system. The implementation of a single biometric system in the country will simplify the payment system and increase access to data.

The corporate websites of hotels and restaurants in Uzbekistan need to be improved. The sites of foreign hotels meet the requirements of world standards, but the sites of local and foreign restaurants in the country, the pages of social networks must be maintained by professionals at the required level, hindering the development of Internet marketing in these entities.

REFERENCES

- 1) <https://vir-tur.ru/statistika/>
- 2) <https://www.terabayt.uz/post/ozbekiston-muzeylariga-endi-dunyoning-istalgan-nuqtasidan-onlayn-sayohat-qilish-mumkin>
- 3) Vishnevskaya E. V. Trends in the development of online tourism. Actual problems of the development of economic, financial and credit systems: collection of materials of the VII International Scientific and Practical Conference (Belgorod, September 12, 2019) / under scientific. ed. : O.V. Vaganova. - Belgorod: Publishing House "BelGU" NRU "BelSU", 2019. - 192 p.
- 4) Gamilyanova E.F. The Online Tourism Phenomenon: An Analysis of Practice. https://elar.urfu.ru/bitstream/10995/62558/1/ttt_2018_16.pdf Sofronov, Bogdan. (2018). The impact of online environment on tourism. Annals of Spiru Haret University Economic Series. 18. 231. 10.26458/18112.
- 5) Belwal, Rakesh & Singh, Gurmeet. (2005). Online tourism and travel-analyzing trends from marketing perspective. Skyline Business Journal. 3. 14-21.
- 6) www.uzairways.com
- 7) <https://uzbektourism.uz/cyrl/newnews/view?id=964>
- 8) <https://www.hyatt.com/en-US/hotel/uzbekistan/hyatt-regency-tashkent/tasrt/area-attractions>
- 9) <https://www.radissonhotels.com/en-us/hotels/radisson-tashkent/rooms?checkInDate=2021-03-17&checkOutDate=2021-03-18&adults%5B%5D=1&children%5B%5D=0&searchType=lowest&promotionCode=>
- 10) <https://www.tripadvisor.ru/>
- 11) <https://tripsecrets.ru/50-luchshih-onlajn-servisov-dlya-puteshestvennikov/>
- 12) <https://www.gazeta.uz/uz/2020/12/11/internet-users/>